

An efficient enantioselective synthesis of argentilactone[†]

P. Veeraraghavan Ramachandran*, M. Venkat Ram Reddy and Herbert C. Brown*

H. C. Brown and R. B. Wetherill Laboratories of Chemistry, Purdue University, West Lafayette, Indiana 47907-1393, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 26 October 1999

Asymmetric allylboration of 2-octynal with (+)-*B*-allyldiisopinocampheylborane provides the corresponding homoallylic alcohol in 80% yield. The alkynol is stereoselectively hydrogenated in the presence of Lindlar catalyst, converted to the corresponding acrylic ester, and cyclized by refluxing in dichloromethane in the presence of 10 mol% of Grubbs' catalyst to provide the natural enantiomer of (*R*)-(-)-argentilactone in 44% overall yield.

A large number of pharmaceutically important organic molecules contain a lactenone or lactone moiety¹. These moieties can be transformed readily to other functional groups providing major target molecules². One such molecule bearing a lactenone moiety is (-)-(5*R*)-5-hydroxydodeca-*Z,Z*,6-dienoic acid lactone (argentilactone, **1**), a major constituent of the extract of the rhizomes, *Aristolochia argentina* and the roots of a liana from French Guyana³, *Annona haematantha* Miq.⁴. This compound, originally reported as a skin irritant has now been shown to possess *in vitro* activity against various strains of *Leishmania* specie, such as *L. donovani*, *L. major*, and *L. amazonensis*, exhibiting a potency similar to that of *N*-methylglucamine antimonate⁴.

There have been only four reports of the chiral synthesis of **1**⁵⁻⁸. All of these chiral substrate-based syntheses do not involve the creation of the lone chiral center in the molecule. In fact, three of these procedures destroy existing chiral centers. All of these syntheses involve the Wittig reaction as the key step for the formation of the *Z*-alkene. O'Connor and Just⁵ reported the synthesis of **1** starting with the acetonide of a chiral olefinic diol (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Carretero and Ghosez⁶ carried out the Wittig reaction of (*R*)-glycerol acetonide early in their sequence and completed their seven-step synthesis in an overall yield of 27.5% (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Rahman and coworkers⁷ began their synthesis from a chiral hydroxybicyclo[3.2.0]heptanone. A photolytic cleavage converts the starting material with four chiral centers to the saturated lactone. This was converted to **1** with one chiral center by three successive reaction sequences, ozonolysis, Wittig, and olefination (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Honda and coworkers⁸ have synthesized **1** starting with the lactol derived from (2*S*,3*R*)-1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-3-(2-furyl)glycerol in 11 steps (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

During the past decade, we have developed several versatile pinane-based chiral organoborane reagents that have found wide applications for enantioselective and diastereoselective organic syntheses (Scheme 5)⁹. Among these, our allyl- and crotylborane reagents have been applied in key

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Scheme 5. Pinane-based versatile reagents.

steps in several important syntheses^{10,11}. As part of our ongoing program involving the synthesis of lactones¹², we decided to undertake the preparation of **1**.

Results and Discussion

Our synthetic protocol is shown in Scheme 6. Our pinane reagent-based synthesis of **1** began with the allylboration of the commercially available 2-octynal (**2**) with (+)-*B*-allyldiisopinocampheylborane (**3**) in diethyl ether-pentane mixture (1 : 1) at -100° . We chose the (+)-reagent, prepared from (-)- α -pinene, since this is known to provide the expected (*R*)-homoallyl alcohol (**4**)¹⁰. Indeed, the alkaline H_2O_2 oxidation of the allylbored product provided the (*R*)-**4** in 80% yield and in 99% ee. The enantiomeric excess was determined by HPLC analysis of its *p*-nitrobenzoate with a CHIRALCEL[®] OD-HT[™] column¹³ using isopropanol : hexane (1 : 99) at 254 nm (UV detector). The racemic peaks were observed at 8.7 and 10.11 min, respectively, with a flow rate of 1 ml/min. The racemic homoallylic alcohol necessary for the analysis was prepared by treating **2** with allylmagnesium bromide.

The homoallylic ynol **4** was converted to the corresponding *Z*-enol **5** in 90% yield by hydrogenating under Lindlar conditions. Although the thin layer chromatographic analysis of the reaction mixture showed a single spot, ¹H NMR analysis revealed ~10% of an impurity¹⁴. This was then converted to the corresponding acryloyl ester (**6**) in 88% yield by treatment with acryloyl chloride in the presence of Et_3N . The closure of **6** to the 6-substituted-5,6-dihydro-2*H*-pyran-2-one **1** was achieved via a ring-closing metathesis¹⁵. Of the several catalysts available for this purpose, we chose

Grubbs' bis(tricyclohexylphosphine)benzylidene ruthenium(IV) dichloride (**7**)¹⁶, due to its commercial availability and the demonstrated success of this reagent. Treatment of **6** with 10 mol% of **7** in refluxing CH_2Cl_2 , after workup provided 70% of **1**¹⁷. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR matched well

Scheme 6. Borane route to argenticlactone.

with those reported in the literature. The rotation, $[\alpha]_D = -21.24$, is in agreement with the maximum rotation, $[\alpha]_D = -21.1$, reported in the literature for **1** isolated from natural sources³.

In conclusion, we have carried out the synthesis of *R*-(-)-argenticlactone in 99% ee via a sequential asymmetric allylboration-hydrogenation-esterification-ring-closing metathesis. The antipode of this lactone can be synthesized by using the enantiomer of **3**. We believe that this four-step reaction sequence is considerably simpler compared to the four procedures currently available in the literature for the synthesis of **1**.

Experimental

All operations were carried out under an inert atmosphere. Techniques for handling air- and moisture-sensitive materials have been previously described¹⁸. The ¹H, ¹¹B and ¹³C NMR spectra were plotted on a Varian Gemini-300 spectrometer with a Nalorac-Quad probe. Mass spectra were recorded using with a Hewlett-Packard 5989B mass spectrometer/5890 series II gas chromatograph or a Finnigan 4000 mass spectrometer. CI gas used was isobutane. The optical rotations were measured using a Rudolph Autopol III polarimeter.

Anhydrous ethyl ether (Et_2O) (Mallinckrodt, Inc.) was used as received. CH_2Cl_2 was distilled over CaH_2 . DIP-Chloride[™]¹⁹, allylmagnesium bromide, 2-octynal, Lindlar's catalyst and acryloyl chloride (all Aldrich Chemical) and Grubbs' catalyst (Strem Chemicals) were used.

1-Undec-5-yn-4-ol (4): Allylmagnesium bromide (72.6 ml, 1.0 *M*, 72.6 mmol) was added dropwise to a well-stirred solution of (+)-DIP-Chloride[™] (24.45 g, 76.2 mmol) in

Et₂O (200 ml) at -78°. The mixture was then stirred for 0.5 h at -78°, allowed to warm to RT, and stirred for 4 h. The solvent was removed under aspirator vacuum, the residue was extracted with pentane (3×150 ml), filtered through a Kramer filter¹⁸, and concentrated to afford ¹Ipc₂BAil (3) (¹¹B NMR δ 79 ppm) in essentially quantitative yield. The reagent was dissolved in pentane to make a 2 M solution. The above ¹Ipc₂BAil (22 mmol, 11 ml) was dissolved in Et₂O to make Et₂O-pentane (1 : 1) and cooled to -100°. A solution of 2-octynal (2.5 g, 20 mmol) in anhydrous Et₂O (5 ml) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was stirred at -100° for 1 h when the reaction was complete (¹¹B NMR shift from δ 79 to 52 ppm). Addition of methanol (1 ml) to this intermediate, followed by the usual work up with NaOH and H₂O₂ afforded the crude product which was extracted with Et₂O, washed with brine and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The pure product was separated from isopinocampheol by silica gel column chromatography (hexane : ethyl acetate :: 95 : 5) to obtain (*R*)-(-)-undec-1-ene-5-yn-4-ol (4; 2.66 g, 16 mmol, 80%) as a liquid. Analysis of its *p*-nitrobenzoate on a CHIRALCEL® OD-H™ HPLC column¹³ using isopropanol : hexane (1 : 99) at 254 nm (UV detector) revealed the % ee to be 99% : IR ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 3412, 2932, 2224, 1641 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 0.89 (3H, t, *J* 7.11 Hz, CH₃), 1.32 (4H, m, (CH₂)₂), 1.49 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.17 (3H, m, CH₂-CH=CH₂, and OH), 2.43 (2H, t, *J* 6.57 Hz, CH₂-C≡C), 4.39 (1H, m, CHOH), 5.16 (2H, m, olefinic), 5.87 (1H, m, olefinic); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 13.96, 18.64, 22.19, 28.35, 31.03, 42.56, 61.80, 80.64, 85.91, 118.54, 133.45; [α]_D²⁴ = -12.52 (*c* 1.5, EtOH); MS EI *m/z* 149 (M-OH⁺), 125, 81, 55 (100%); CI *m/z* 167 (M+H)⁺, 149 (100%).

1,5Z-Undecadien-4-ol (5) : Lindlar's catalyst (50 mg) and quinoline (50 mg) were taken in a 25-ml round-bottomed flask, followed by the addition of methanol (10 ml) and 4 (1.0 g, 6 mmol dissolved in 1 ml MeOH). The flask was purged with hydrogen and closed under a positive pressure of hydrogen. The reaction was monitored by the consumption of hydrogen using a gasimeter. Upon completion (~0.5 h), the reaction mixture was filtered, the solvent removed, and purified by silica gel column chromatography to afford 5 as a liquid : IR ν_{max} (neat) 3346, 2918, 1638, 1458, 1027 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) 0.89 (3H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz, CH₃), 1.35 (6H, m, (CH₂)₃), 1.71 (1H, br s, OH), 2.08 (2H, m, CH₂-C=C), 2.28 (2H, m, CH₂-C=C), 4.48 (1H, m), 5.13 (2H, m, olefinic), 5.44 (2H, m, olefinic), 5.81 (1H, m, olefinic); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) 14.03, 22.53, 27.72, 29.35, 31.49, 42.15, 66.90, 117.97, 131.69, 132.66, 134.36; MS EI *m/z* 151 (M-OH⁺),

127, 109, 67, 57 (100%); CI *m/z* 167 (M-H)⁺, 151 (100%), 127, 109, 95.

Esterification of 5 : To 5 (1.0 g, 6 mmol) dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (15 ml) and cooled to 0°, were added acryloyl chloride (0.74 ml, 9.0 mmol) and Et₃N (2.50 ml, 18 mmol). The mixture was warmed to RT and stirred for 4 h. The resulting mixture was filtered through a short pad of celite to remove solid Et₃N•HCl, poured into water, and the product extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (hexane : ethyl acetate :: 99 : 1) and concentrated to obtain 6 (1.17 g, 88%) : IR ν_{max} (neat) 2925, 1722, 1635, 1404, 1268, 1187 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6.74 Hz, CH₃), 1.29 (6H, m, (CH₂)₃), 2.15 (2H, m, CH₂-C=C), 2.40 (2H, m, CH₂-C=C), 5.09 (1H, m, olefinic), 5.36 (1H, m, olefinic), 5.67 (4H, m, olefinic), 6.10 (1H, dd, *J* 10.29, 10.29 Hz, olefinic), 6.39 (1H, dd, *J* 17.4, 1.44 Hz, olefinic); ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) 14.04, 22.54, 27.94, 29.16, 31.49, 39.37, 69.80, 117.93, 127.22, 128.88, 130.40, 133.21, 134.71, 163.51; MS EI *m/z* 181 (M-C₃H₅⁺), 109, 79, 55 (100%); CI *m/z* 222 (M⁺), 151 (100%).

Argentilactone (1) : Grubbs' catalyst (0.16 g, 0.02 mmol, 10 mol%) dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (5 ml) was added dropwise to a refluxing solution of the above acrylic ester (0.44 g, 2 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (200 ml). Refluxing was continued for 6 h by which time all of the starting material was consumed (TLC). The solvent was removed under aspirator vacuum and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (hexane : ethylacetate :: 75 : 25) to obtain 1 (0.27 g, 70%) : IR ν_{max} (neat) 2925, 1718, 1377, 1241, 1020 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6.75 Hz, CH₃), 1.32 (6H, m, (CH₂)₃), 2.08 (2H, m, CH₂-C=C), 2.39 (2H, m, CH₂-C=C), 5.22 (1H, m, CH-O), 5.61 (2H, m, olefinic), 6.04 (1H, dt, *J* 9.75, 2.25 Hz, cyclic olefinic), 6.89 (1H, m, cyclic olefinic); ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) 14.0, 22.48, 27.77, 29.05, 29.92, 31.38, 73.92, 121.51, 126.42, 135.64, 144.98, 164.21; [α]_D²⁵ = -21.24 (*c* 1.5, EtOH); MS EI *m/z* 194 (M⁺), 152, 97, 68 (100%); CI *m/z* 195 (M+H)⁺ (100%).

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from the Purdue Borane Research Fund is acknowledged.

References

1. H. M. R. Hoffman and J. Rabe, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1985, 24, 94.
2. A. K. Ghosh and C. Liu, *Chem. Commun.*, 1999, 1743.
3. H. A. Priestap, J. D. Bonafede and E. A. Ruveda, *Phytochemistry*, 1977, 16, 1579.

4. A. I. Waechter, M. E. Ferreira, A. Fournet, A. R. de Arias, H. Nakayama, S. Torres, R. Hocquemiller and A. Cavé, *Planta Medica*, 1997, **63**, 433.
5. B. O'Connor and G. Just, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 5201.
6. J. C. Carretero and L. Ghosez, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1988, **29**, 2059.
7. S. S. Rahman, B. J. Wakefield, S. M. Roberts and M. D. Dowle, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1989, 303.
8. M. Tsubuki, K. Kanai and T. Honda, *Heterocycles*, 1993, **35**, 281.
9. (a) H. C. Brown and P. V. Ramachandran in "Advances in Asymmetric Synthesis", ed. A. Hassner, JAI Press, Greenwich, 1995, Vol. 1, Chap. 5; (b) H. C. Brown and P. V. Ramachandran, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1995, **500**, 1.
10. H. C. Brown and P. K. Jadhav, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 2092.
11. H. C. Brown and K. S. Bhat, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 293.
12. (a) H. C. Brown, S. V. Kulkarni and U. S. Racherla, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1994, **59**, 365; (b) P. V. Ramachandran, G. M. Chen and H. C. Brown, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 2205; (c) P. V. Ramachandran, M. P. Krzeminski, M. V. R. Reddy and H. C. Brown, *Tetrahedron Asym.*, 1999, **10**, 11; (d) P. V. Ramachandran, M. V. R. Reddy and H. C. Brown, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **41**, 0000.
13. CHIRALCEL® OD-HT™ is a product of Chiral Technologies, Inc., Exton, PA, U.S.A.
14. Due to the lack of polarity difference we did not make any attempts to isolate the side-product. We proceeded to the next step with the mixture. We presume the impurity is the terminal double bond reduction product on the basis of mass spectrometry (m/z 170, M^+).
15. (a) 'Olefin Metathesis in Organic Synthesis', *Tetrahedron Symposia in Print* #73, *Tetrahedron*, 1999, **55**, 8141; (b) D. L. Wright, *Curr. Org. Chem.*, 1999, **3**, 211, and references cited therein.
16. G. C. Fu and R. H. Grubbs, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **114**, 5426.
17. About 15% of unreacted starting material was recovered.
18. H. C. Brown, G. W. Kramer, A. B. Levy and M. M. Midland, "Organic Syntheses via Boranes", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1975 : Reprinted edition, Aldrich Chemical Co. Inc., Milwaukee, 1997, Vol. 1, Chap. 9.
19. H. C. Brown, J. Chandrasekharan and P. V. Ramachandran, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 1539; DIP-Chloride™ is a Trade-mark of Aldrich Chemical Company.